

Learning Disability in an Organization- A Disruption to Indian Business

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Abstract

Learning incapacities are disastrous in youngsters, particularly when they are undetected. It is more deplorable in associations where they go to a great extent undetected. The initial phase in relieving them is to start recognizing the seven learning disabilities "I am my position", "the foe is out there", the hallucination of assuming responsibility, the obsession with occasions, The laws of the fifth discipline .

Keywords: learning organization, personal mastery.

Introduction

An organization cannot improve unless it learns continuously in order to survive. learning is a journey and not an end in itself. The human resource in the organization play a vital role in determining where the organization stands. Studies have shown that as we grow older we our learning ability is declined. As a child we learn and grasp from our environment constantly. But, as we grow older our ability to learn and adapt to our environment is severely declined.

In an organization, human resource that is incapable of learning is as good as dead corpse. One must constantly work on themselves, improve and develop to their fullest potential.

Objective

An investigation into the degree of learning handicap in associations and propose implies by which associations can enhance and learn constantly through:

- To recognize the learning inability of the workforce.
- To order the workforce into the control of individual authority.
- To propose the elements distinguished to be foundations of a learning association.

Methodology

- Sample: 68 out of which 50 responded.
- Sampling techniques: Questionnaire (open and close ended)
- Method of data collection: Primary and secondary data.

Literature Review

PETER M SENGE has mentioned in his book that few organizations live only half if a person, this is due to the learning disabilities found in an organization. It is no accident that most organizations learn poorly. The ways they are designed and managed, the way people's jobs are defined create learning disabilities.

Scope of the Study

The study intends to cover- identifying learning disabilities at an early stage and take measures to overcome these disabilities in an organization

Limitations of the Study

- The data provided may mostly depend on the perception of the subjects
- The study is based on limited number of subjects.
- Time was an important limitation for collecting data on a larger scale.
- Not all organisations/ start-ups have a HR department.

To list out a few, here are the learning disabilities found in an organization:

Learning Disabilities (Findings)

1. "I am my Position"

This syndrome is exhibited by an employee when he is too comfortable at his job and doesn't want to expand and learn more in order to improve himself. This can often lead to boredom, routine work and ultimately lack of motivation and loyalty towards the company.

2. "The Enemy is out There"

We often tend to blame others before checking ourselves. For example in an organization the production department blames the marketing, the marketing department blames the suppliers and so on so forth. One must always check before pointing fingers because it is of no help in solving the situation. Accepting a mistake and taking measures to correct it is important in solving the issue then and there before it gets bigger.

3. "The Illusion of Taking Charge"

People often identify that there is a problem and do nothing about it. This is called not taking charge or not being proactive. Employees are under the assumption that if they can see a problem others can see it too, hence others can fix it and they need not worry about it. This can be very dangerous to the organization when such problems go undetected. Being proactive is very important in reducing additional cost to the organization and also helps to give the employees recognition.

4. "The Fixation on Events"

We are adapted to consider life to be a progression of occasions, and for each occasion, we think here is one clear reason. Generative learning can't be managed in an association if individuals' reasoning is commanded by here and now occasions. In the event that associations center around occasions all the better they can do is to foresee an occasion before it occurs so they can respond ideally.

6. "The Delusion of Learning from Experience"

We are often told that the best learning happens through experiences. But what if these experiences are in the future? For example the decisions taken today will not give results in the present but the results will be seen in the future which is not controllable and one must wait a long time to experience the results of their actions and learn from their experience.

7. "The Myth of Management Team"

It is often assumed that the management is the higher authority in decision making- which is true; but that doesn't mean the employees have no say in the decision making. If an employee

has a genuine reason as to why certain decision is wrong he must be given a fair hearing by the management team. individuals with genuine reservations abstain from expressing them publically, and joint choices are diluted bargains reflecting what everybody can live with.

Keeping in mind the end goal to conquer these learning inabilities, one must take after the control of individual dominance and furthermore know about the foundations of the learning association:

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1.1 Showing employees willingness to change roles in an organization

Employee`s willingness to change roles	Yes, I am willing to learn and change roles	No, I am not comfortable with change and will continue to play my role in the organization
No of Respondents	39	11

Source: survey data

Source: excel output

Table 1.1 depicts that 39 out of 50 are willing to accept change, learn and play a different role in the organization. Such employees are motivated, loyal and ambitious, they are willing to try new things and learn as much as possible.

However, 11 out of 50 are not willing to change and are comfortable in the present roles they have assumed in the organization. Few employees are very comfortable in their role and are afraid to take up additional responsibility. They are portraying “I AM MY POSITION” syndrome.

Table 1.2 Portraying the ‘enemy is out there’ syndrome

Employee`s willingness to blame others (other department)	Yes, I would blame others for I have done my part well.	No, I would take the blame even if I have done my part well
No of respondents	31	19

Source: survey data

Source: excel output

Table 1.2 depicts that 31 out of 50 are willing to put the blame on others (other department) when the organization faces a hiccup in its performance. Every individual has self-esteem and as human beings we tend to blame others before we check ourselves.

However, 19 out of 50 wouldn't blame, rather check their work once again. It is always best to crosscheck one's own work and work together to solve an issue before starting the blame game.

Table 1.3 Showing employees being proactive or not

Employee's willingness to take charge of a situation	Yes, I would be proactive in solving the situation	No, I would let someone else take charge of the situation
No of respondents	26	24

Source: survey data

Source: excel output

Table 1.3 depicts 26 out of 50 are willing to take charge of a situation and try to handle it rather than wait for others to take charge of the situation.

Every individual seeks recognition in an organization and to be recognized, one has to be proactive, take charge of the situation and try to solve it rather than waiting for somebody else to do it. Identifying an issue and doing nothing about assuming somebody else will identify and solve it can cause losses to an organization. However, 24 out of 50 are willing to let somebody else take charge of the situation. This can be because the employees lack loyalty, motivation, and only do what they are asked to do, no more no less.

Conclusion

We live in a society that is constantly upgrading, innovating and being more competitive. An organization cannot survive if its employees are lethargic and have no motivation or loyalty towards the organization. Studies have shown that on an average 500 companies every day are shutting down due to their inability to learn and grow. In such organization learning disabilities prevail. These disabilities must be identified and corrected at the earliest else the organization will cease to exist. this paper can help identify and categorize the employees into 7 categories depending on the disabilities they showcase and take measures in curbing these disabilities to make the organization a competitive one.

Implications of this study on the present and future organizations

- This study can immensely help start-ups and other organizations to sustain in the market and have a competitive advantage.
- This study can easily help one identify and categorize disabilities found in an organization into broadly 7 categories or disabilities.
- This study also suggests certain disciplines of personal mastery, which when organizations follow consistently, they can surely succeed.
- This study helps employees understand the business, get out of their shell, have an impact on the organization and be a strategic business partner.

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